

Philippine Science High School
Main Campus

Scoliosis Detection Using Kinect With Machine Learning

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With Machine Learning

by

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ABSTRACT

The current clinical standard for scoliosis detection is manual assessment of the Cobb Angle from radiographic images. This method is time-consuming, unaffordable, invasive (subjects the patient to high levels of radiation when done frequently), and not viable for mass screenings. Manually solving for the Cobb Angle is also prone to intra- and inter-observer errors. Using the depth sensing applications of the Microsoft Xbox Kinect and the data processing capabilities of machine learning algorithms, the research aims to develop a scoliosis detection program that is fast, inexpensive, non-invasive, and user-friendly. The detection program made use of four alternative scoliosis assessment algorithms called 'trunk surface metrics' developed in earlier studies, namely the 1) Shoulder Angle Alignment, 2) Body Alignment, 3) Posterior Trunk Symmetry Index, and 4) Deformity in the Axial Plane Index. A decision tree, based on the C4.5 algorithm, for data analysis will be developed. A preliminary testing of 26 participants was implemented to calibrate the program and train a decision tree based on the C4.5 algorithm. A final testing of 60 participants will be implemented to determine sensitivity and specificity of the program. In conclusion, the results of the study show the potential of using depth-sensing technologies and machine learning algorithms for scoliosis screening and other biomechanical applications.

APPROVAL SHEET

This research work entitled, “**Scoliosis Detection Using Kinect with Machine Learning**” by Jose Ignacio A. Locsin, Christine Joy C. Okubo, and Romeo Jose B. Quisto, presented to the Faculty of the Philippine Science High School – Main Campus in partial fulfillment of the requirements in Science and Technology Research 2, is hereby accepted.

Name of Research Adviser Here
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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Scoliosis is the abnormal sideward curvature of the spine that appears during the onset of adolescence. It is the most common spinal deformity which affects around 3% of children worldwide. The underlying cause for scoliosis is still unknown (Wise, Gao, Shoemaker, Gordon & Herring, 2008).

The Cobb Angle Method is the current clinical standard for scoliosis assessment. It has been understood that the Cobb Angle Method only describes scoliosis, a 3-dimensional deformity, in one plane, limiting the observation to one aspect. Additionally, the Cobb Angle Method involves invasive procedures such as a physical examination and X-ray imaging (Kotwicki, 2008). Thus, it is time-consuming and expensive. Furthermore, the examination is done manually by healthcare professionals by measuring the angles on the radiographic images. Studies have proven that the method is prone to intra- and inter-observer errors (Langensiepen et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2010).

Depth imaging is a recent technological advancement that allows the comprehensive analysis of visual data through the collection of images in real time and the detection of variations in object distance (Tiangang, Zhou, Xinyang, & Yi, 2013). It has been used in video games, biomechanics and simultaneous mapping, among others, and its numerous and diverse application possibilities have made it popular in several research fields (Ren, Yuan, Meng, & Zhang, 2013; Khoshelham, & Elberink, 2012).

Alternative scoliosis assessment techniques, which focus on back surface topography and the use of depth imaging, have been developed in order to characterize the scoliosis in 3

planes: sagittal, coronal and transverse, giving a wider perspective on the scoliotic deformity.

The developed techniques include Moire-Fringe Mapping, the integrated Shape imaging System and the Trunk Surface Metrics (Patias, Grivas, Kaspiris, Aggouris & Drakoutos, 2010).

The current clinical standard for diagnosing for scoliosis with X-ray imaging is time-consuming, expensive and invasive. Ko, Lee, Chae, and Pan (2012) have explored the feasibility of using Microsoft Kinect, a cheap and user-friendly depth sensor, as an instrument for diagnosing scoliosis. The Kinect can produce a depth image of a person's back and using Trunk Surface Metrics, it can detect for scoliosis without the use of X-ray imaging.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of this study is to develop an inexpensive, non-invasive, and user-friendly alternative method for scoliosis detection with the precise mapping and depth-sensing applications of the Microsoft Kinect. To achieve this, the detection program developed in the previous research, Using Kinect to Detect Scoliosis, will be reviewed and improved by adding more trunk surface metric algorithms and incorporating machine learning. Preliminary testing involving students from the Philippine Science High School - Main Campus will be conducted to test the accuracy of the program. Decision Tree algorithms will be used to improve the method and create an empirical threshold angle using data from the study's preliminary testing.

Significance of the Study

The program created will be geared specifically towards user-friendliness and will be comprehensive and specialized and leave little work to be done on the part of the user. It would also remove the need for X-ray imaging procedures and would enable the detection of scoliosis

without substantial fees and without the presence of an expert. In addition, the Kinect sensor is affordable and therefore easily accessible. As a result, the developed method would be both home and school-friendly, facilitating the early detection of scoliosis. Detecting scoliosis during the pubescent years is essential to prevent the worsening of scoliosis.

Scope and Limitations

The population of the study comprises only of Philippine Science High School - Main Campus students, aged 13-18. Recalibration and training using a new data set may be necessary if the program is used on participants from a different population (such as a different age group).

The limitations of this preliminary study includes a small sample size for the preliminary testing, a need for further refinement of the trunk surface metrics, and the lack of a machine learning program for data analysis. The target number of participants for the preliminary testing was 40 participants. However, only 26 participants were obtained to participate in the preliminary testing because of time constraints. Additionally, some of the selected participants did not choose to participate.

The algorithms for the four trunk surface metrics used are not yet robust and need a recalibration before the final testing. Moreover, the DAPI does not work consistently. This may have been because of an undocumented fault in one of the Kinect Source Development Kit's functions, which the DAPI algorithm relies heavily on. Further work is needed is needed on the DAPI algorithm to bypass the use of this function.

For this preliminary study, no machine learning program was used to analyze the results obtained from the testing. The decision tree algorithm is still being built and trained. The results presented in this paper are only index values compared to threshold values. Accordingly, the

researchers do not declare the data gathered definite indicators of whether or not a sample is scoliotic or non-scoliotic but rather, a representative of probability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scoliosis

Scoliosis is a physical deformity characterized by the rotation of the spine resulting in abnormal sideways spine curvature (Newson, 2014). The curvatures are often C-shaped or S-shaped. These sideways curves often follow a certain pattern which professionals have studied. According to the National Institute of Arthritis and Musculoskeletal and Skin Diseases (2018), the curves can either be thoracic, lumbar, thoracolumbar, or double which states that there is a curve at the thoracic and lumbar part of the torso.

Types of Scoliosis

Most cases of scoliosis have their origins unknown and this is called idiopathic scoliosis (Baaj, 2017). Rare cases of scoliosis are congenital which is caused by the deformity of the formation of the spine in the womb. Neuromuscular scoliosis is another type of scoliosis which is caused by neuromuscular conditions such as cerebral palsy or muscular dystrophy (Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research, 2018). Degenerative scoliosis is caused by the spine's degeneration as a person grows older.

Early Detection of Scoliosis

The signs of scoliosis include: a visibly curved spine, uneven shoulders, one side of a hip or shoulder sticking out, or the ribs sticking out on one side (NHS, n.d.). Scoliosis usually develops during the growth spurt just before puberty. Early detection of scoliosis will help prevent the worsening of symptoms such as body pains, headache, poor posture, and severe cases such as breathing and heart problems.

Cobb Angle

The standard method of scoliosis diagnosis is the Cobb angle method which makes use of an X-ray of the back . First, lines are drawn along the top of the superior tilted vertebra and the bottom of the inferior tilted vertebra. Then, lines perpendicular to the previous lines are drawn. The angle of the intersection of these lines is the Cobb angle (CLEAR Scoliosis Institute, 2017). There are three degrees of scoliosis: mild, moderate and severe (What is Scoliosis, n.d.). Cobb angles 25 degrees below are considered mild, 25 to 40 are moderate, and greater than 40 degrees are severe.

Depth Imaging

Depth Imaging with a depth-sensing camera can be used to create 3-dimensional topographical images of the shape of the back surface. (Oxborrow, 2000) This method of measurement only requires an optical device and thus, does not expose patients to ionizing radiation.

Depth imaging technology, commonly used in mapping applications, has been seeing more and more use in the field of medicine. One of the emergent applications for such technology is in physical therapy and rehabilitation. Depth cameras and similar sensor technologies can be used to help monitor and correct exercises while also allowing a wider range of interactions between patients, therapists, and the software unlike previous input devices which require physical contact and limit movement. (Lange, Rizzo, Chang, Suma, & Bolas, 2011)

Kinect sensor

The Kinect sensor is an advanced game sensor which incorporates three types of cameras: color, depth and infrared, and also supports audio input. It has several capabilities

including body tracking, 3D mapping and facial, audio and gesture recognition. Due to its many applications, it is widely used not only in the gaming industry but only in other fields (Zhang, 2012). Although producing results of low accuracy in tracking dancers in a virtual reality system possibly due to quick changes in position and poor calibration, it has shown multiple applications on human biometrics (Alexiadis, Kelly, Daras, O'Connor, Boubekour, & Moussa, 2011). To properly detect human bodies, the Kinect has a prescribed sensing range which is 1.2 to 3.5 m (Dutta, 2012)

Moire Topography

Moire topography is a mapping technique that makes use of the alternating light and dark bands or contour lines formed on the surface of an object by shining a light through a screen with vertical and parallel strips. This can be done by illuminating an object from two different point sources can create contour maps of the surface of the object.. The Moire method is very sensitive to asymmetries. Moire fringe deviation analysis is used to detect and characterize asymmetry on a surface (Ruggerone & Austin, 1986). The moiré method can be used for scoliosis diagnosis by observing contour maps of the back surface and looking at asymmetries (Willner, 1979).

Artificial Neural Network

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is configured for a specific application, such as pattern recognition or data classification, through a learning process. Learning in ANNs involves adjustments to the connections that exist between the neurons similar to how it is in biological systems (Stergiou & Siganos). Machine learning is a way of creating Artificial Intelligence (A. I.) through improving the performance of a machine. Its goal is to automate by building special-purpose systems (Nilsson, 2005).

Algorithms

Algorithms are a major component of machine learning (Ayodele, 2010). Machine learning requires an algorithm to function. There are six types of algorithms based on how they handle given inputs: (1) supervised learning, (2) unsupervised learning, (3) semi-supervised learning, (4) reinforcement learning, (5) transduction, and (6) learning to learn. These algorithms may further be classified into multiple learning methods based on the analysis and mathematical presentation of data (Ayodele, 2010).

Training

Training involves feeding the machine a set of data to learn for the development of an algorithm which will be used on a testing data set (Ayodele, 2010). The machine assumes that the testing data set is a representative of the distribution of the actual data. The testing data is used for the development of classifiers and models. The performance and accuracy of the model is then tested to a completely different testing data set. (Witten, Frank, Hall, & Pal, 2016).

Decision Tree

The decision tree is a method of machine learning that categorizes data into groups based on machine-determined characteristics (Ayodele, 2010). It creates a classifier based on randomly selected variables. It is not prone to overfitting data, however highly sensitive on the sampling technique (Belgiu & Drăguț, 2016). It can analyze and mine patterns from raw input data (Sathyadevan & Nair, 2015).

Alternative Scoliosis Assessments

Current methods for diagnosis are costly, time consuming and the patients are exposed to radiation. Alternative non-invasive scoliosis assessments are continuously being developed.

These methods often use structured light or optical measurement techniques to lessen the number of radiographic examinations needed. (Minguez, Buendia, Cibrian, Salvador, Lagua, Martin, & Gomar, 2007).

Posterior Trunk Symmetry Index

The Posterior Trunk Symmetry Index (POTSI) is a variable which quantifies the length differences and asymmetry of parts of the back along the frontal plane to detect scoliosis. (Suzuki, Inami, Ono, Kohno, & Asher, 1999) POTSI calculations can be done from a single photo of a patient's exposed back. Because, it mainly uses body landmarks and length ratios, it is not affected by a growth or size. POTSI is reported to have low sensitivity and high specificity, meaning that it can better tell the absence of scoliosis. (Kotwicki, 2008)

Deformity in the Axial Plane Index

The Deformity in the Axial Plane Index (DAPI) quantifies depth differences and left-right asymmetry of certain parts of the back along the transverse plane. Similar to POTSI, DAPI is not affected by patient's size or growth. It is reported to have high sensitivity and low specificity, meaning that it can better determine the presence of scoliosis. DAPI and POTSI have complementary diagnostic strengths and weaknesses. (Minguez et.al., 2007)

Shoulder and Hip Angles Analysis

Uneven shoulders and hips are some of the most easily observable symptoms of scoliosis. Analysis of shoulder and hip angles could then be a viable method for assessing spinal posture and could serve as an initial test for scoliosis and other spinal deformities. (Castro, Pacheco, Lourenço, Queirós, Moreira, Rodrigues, & Vilaça, 2017)

METHODOLOGY

Process Flowchart

Figure 1. Level 0 general process flowchart

Reevaluation of previous algorithms

The algorithms developed in the previous research, Using Kinect to Detect Scoliosis, was reviewed. The algorithms was used within the Kinect Software Development Kit and data was obtained through a Kinect V2 sensor. The previous code was revised to include visualizations of points of interests. The accuracy and consistency was confirmed by running the program in real time with a willing participant in order to ensure that the correct points of interests were being taken. For example, the array of body pixels should align with the body of the participant.

Improvement of measuring algorithms

Based on the reevaluation of the previous algorithms, the code was optimized, revised, replaced or left unchanged. Some bases for optimization and revision was found in studies done by Ko, Lee, Chae and Pan (n.d.), Kim, Ishikawa, Ohtsuka, Shimizu, Shinomiya and Viergever (2001), Nadas Qan, Gal, Crişan-Vida, Nemes, Andrei (2015) and Bonnet, Yamaguchi, Dupeyron, Andary, Seilles, Fraisse, and Venture (2016). One basis for developing a new algorithm is the posterior trunk symmetry index (POTSI) (Mínguez, Buendía, Cibrián, Salvador, Laguía, Martín, & Gomar, 2007).

Participant screening

The population of the study was Philippine Science High School - Main Campus (PSHS-MC) Students, aged 12-18. For the selection of participants in the preliminary testing, one of the researchers identified which students from the PSHS-MC are diagnosed with scoliosis. Only one researcher was aware of which students have scoliosis to avoid bias in the analysis of results for the preliminary testing. High school students or teenagers were selected as participants for this project because development of scoliosis happens during the adolescent phase and early detection is crucial for treatment (Newson, 2014).

Selection and contact of participants

For the preliminary testing, forty (40) students was asked to sign an informed consent indicating that they agreed to the terms and conditions of the testing. A consent form is necessary because the participants will have to be semi-nude, leaving the back exposed. This is a protocol that ensures the accuracy of the produced results as having clothes on will contribute to the deformities detected by the Kinect. Also, since most of the participants are minors, their parent's consent are also required to proceed with the testing. When a selected student or parent refused

to participate, the researchers contacted another student from the list gathered in the participant screening phase of the project. The forty students was divided into males and females in which there will be ten with scoliosis and ten without scoliosis for both genders.

The sample size for the final testing is sixty (60), which larger relative to the sample size for the preliminary testing because the final testing evaluates the accuracy (specificity and sensitivity) of the program which will produce the results of the study. Also, there's a tendency that the machine will overlearn/overfit and produce biased results if the preliminary testing has more participants.

Preliminary testing

The preliminary testing required 40 participants from the students of PSHS- MC. Out of the projected 40 participants, only 26 participants showed up for the preliminary testing.. The participants consisted of 9 scoliotic males, 5 scoliotic females, 9 non-scoliotic males, and 3 non-scoliotic females. A researcher of the same gender as the participant conducted the testing. Testing was done inside Edge Lab which is in the Advanced Science & Technology Building (ASTB) of PSHS-MC. Windows were covered to ensure the privacy of the testing. Data obtained will be used to calibrate the program and train the decision tree.

Development of machine learning algorithms

A C4.5 is a well-known algorithm for generating multivariate decision trees. The C4.5 can handle attributes with discrete or continuous (numerical) values. It helps avoid overfitting by pruning the decision tree right after its creation (Adhatrao, K., Gaykar, A., Dhawan, A., Jha, R., and Honrao, V., 2013).

Application of machine learning

The C4.5 will be used for calibration and data interpretation. Data sets from the preliminary testing will be used to train the algorithm until a final accurate algorithm is derived. Overfitting in the decision tree will be avoided by setting a maximum number participants(40) and age (18) for preliminary testing.

Final testing

The final testing requires 60 participants from the same population (consisting of 15 scoliotic males, 15 scoliotic females, 15 non-scoliotic males, and 15 non-scoliotic females) and will determine the accuracy of the developed program.

Analysis of data and results

One of the researchers will then verify the accuracy and reliability of the program by comparing the results with the information gathered about which participants have scoliosis. The McNemar's test checks the association between the doctor's diagnosis and the Kinect V2's diagnosis. The alpha level will be set to 0.5. The association between the doctor's diagnosis and the Kinect V2's diagnosis is strong if the p-value is less than the alpha level.

The sensitivity and specificity values will be used as the bases for accuracy. Sensitivity and specificity is the true positive and true negative rates. The project will be deemed successful if both sensitivity and specificity values are at least 90%.

Ethical Considerations

The participants' welfare is the top priority throughout the study. Formal letters of consent was given to participants if they wish to participate or not in the study. It contains the purpose and procedure of the study, potential health benefits and/or risks, and financial elements to assure that the participants are well informed. It also reassures the confidentiality of the data

gathered from the participants. The researchers asked for consent before using any of the participant's data. The participant's data was only accessible to the researchers involved in this study. The consent form also states that participation in this study is voluntary and they can opt to withdraw at anytime. The researchers are required to update the Research Ethics Committee of the progress of the research to ensure the ethicality of the research process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The raw index values obtained from the preliminary testing were classified as “Scoliotic” or “Normal” based on threshold values specific to each algorithm. These results were then compared with professional diagnostic results and organized into contingency 2x2 contingency tables.

Since the developed program is designed as a screening test for scoliosis, the sensitivity and specificity values and McNemar’s test were used to analyze the preliminary testing results. A novel screening test is considered good if its sensitivity and specificity values are both at least 90%.

A two-tailed McNemar’s test with $\alpha = 0.05$ was performed to see whether there is a significant difference between the professional diagnosis results and the developed program’s results. The null hypothesis is that there is no significant difference between the results. In the case of this research, obtaining a p-value greater than 0.05 is favorable since this would not reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the developed program’s results do not differ significantly from those of professional diagnosis.

Table 1. Contingency Table for Shoulder Angle Test with Threshold = 2

Actual Kinect Result	Diagnosed with scoliosis	Diagnosed with no scoliosis	TOTAL
“Scoliotic”	11	3	14
“Normal”	3	9	12
TOTAL	14	12	26
p-value	0.68309		

The Shoulder Angle Test had a sensitivity of 78.57% and a specificity of 25%. The obtained p-value of 0.68309 is not enough to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 2. Contingency Table for Body Alignment Test with Threshold = 5

Actual Kinect Result	Diagnosed with scoliosis	Diagnosed with no scoliosis	TOTAL
"Scoliotic"	8	7	15
"Normal"	6	5	11
TOTAL	14	12	26
p-value	1		

The Body Alignment Test had a sensitivity of 57.14% and a specificity of 58.33%. The obtained p-value of 1 is not enough to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 3. Contingency Table for POTSI Test with Threshold = 27.5

Actual Kinect Result	Diagnosed with scoliosis	Diagnosed with no scoliosis	TOTAL
"Scoliotic"	3	0	3
"Normal"	11	12	23
TOTAL	14	12	26
p-value	1		

The POTSI Test had a sensitivity of 21.43% and a specificity of 100%. The obtained p-value of 1 is not enough to reject the null hypothesis.

The DAPI algorithm was unable to consistently deliver results. Only 10 out of the 26 participants had DAPI values. No contingency table was made for DAPI due to this issue. The performance inconsistency was attributed by the DAPI algorithm's failure to identify certain points of interests and was later discovered to be caused by an undocumented fault in the `MapDepthPointToCameraSpace()` function in the Kinect Source Development Kit. As described by Carmine Si, a microsoft employee, in a Microsoft forum post (Si, 2015), the function was not well documented and sometimes returns erroneous values without throwing an exception or warning the system that an error has occurred.

The statistical values for the McNemar's test for all three working algorithms were favorable indicating that the developed program's results do not differ significantly than those of professional diagnosis; however, most of the sensitivity and specificity values are well below the target value of 90%. The difference in the evaluation by McNemar's test and sensitivity and specificity value can be attributed to the low sample size. A total of 25 or more false positives and false negatives is recommended when using McNemar's test to get a well approximated chi-square value. Since there were only 26 participants, the sum of false positives and false negatives were most likely to be less than 25. Also, the results from a low sample size may not appropriately represent the program's true sensitivity and specificity. It is therefore essential to have a larger sample size during the second testing phase of this project.

The raw data tables in Appendix A show multiple data sets for each participant. The data set used for analysis was chosen in the following manner: The mode, accurate up to the ones

digit, was chosen. Multiple runs were done on each participant since they were still prone to slight movements which could vary the results. Runs could be performed in quick succession since results were returned almost instantly after the button press. The mode of all runs can be interpreted as the test value obtained during the time interval when the participant's position was stable. If no mode can be identified, the average of the data, excluding the outliers, was taken as the result to be used in analysis. The need for multiple runs and data set selection emphasizes the need for a proper posture apparatus, similar to the ones used in X-ray examinations, for further work.

It is worth noting that the results presented in this paper are based on threshold values recommended in previous similar studies (Ko et.al., n.d.), (Minguez et.al., 2007), . There is no global consensus or standard threshold used for trunk surface metrics since these methods are relatively new developments that are not yet widely used. The results presented are not to be taken as final diagnoses but rather as measures of probability that a participant may have scoliosis. It is also essential to have readings using different approaches or indices since each trunk surface metric measures deformity in different aspects of scoliosis that may or may not correlate with each other. The raw readings obtained from this project are intended to be fed into a machine learning program which will analyze raw data from different indices to come up with a unified diagnosis.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The developed alternative scoliosis screening method had low sensitivity and specificity values but with favorable McNemar's test p-values. One of the four algorithms failed but the underlying cause was later identified. With a greater sample size, proper posture apparatus and the incorporation of machine learning, a more robust and more accurate screening method could be achieved and could enable the detection of scoliosis even in the absence of professionals and can be used for annual medical school check-ups. The duration of testing for each participant took around one minute each, and the procedure did not involve the insertion of objects into the body or the exposure to any harmful substance, while the only funds needed for the replication of entire project would be for the purchase of a Kinect and a Kinect PC adaptor. Therefore, it can be concluded that the created method is a fast, non-invasive and safe method of diagnosing scoliosis that is cheaper and easier to perform, although currently not yet as reliable as existing methods.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For the final testing of this study, the algorithms of the four trunk surface metrics will further be refined. The researchers will obtain a target sample size of 60 participants or greater.. During the final testing, a posture apparatus will be used to avoid experimental error.

The developed machine learning program will then be used to analyze the data obtained from the final testing based on the characteristics of the population as indicated by the preliminary testing data. The results obtained will then be verified with the medical records of the sample.

For future studies, the researchers recommend the addition of other trunk surface metrics being developed and further refinement of the four trunk surface metrics used. The testing can also be implemented on a larger sample size to be able to ensure that the program is representative of the population. If the number of participants reach thousands, future studies may opt to use a neural network to analyze their data.

The researchers also recommend changing the population of the study to a larger scale. The training and testing of the program on a bigger population accentuates its feasibility to be used for mass screenings. Future researches may collaborate with hospitals or orthopedic clinics for the convenience of sampling and for acquiring a large and diverse set of participants.

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APPENDIX A

Raw Data Set from Preliminary Testing

Table 4: Raw Data Set from Preliminary Testing (Participants with Scoliosis)

PARTICIPANT	TEST	SHOULDER ANGLE DIFFERENCE	BODY ALIGNMENT	POTSI	DAPI
1	1	6.06789	3.07939	9.11346	
	2	6.26858	5.82391	15.5445	
	3	6.91829	9.46128	48.5509	
	4	7.40754	7.18591	22.2204	
2	1	3.28809	11.9243	18.356	
	2	3.34068	20.7919	15.1484	
	3	3.39072	9.12738	0.46911	7.24015
	4	3.43397	7.96946	0.46896	13.1579
3	1	1.35053	10.4927	11.328	
	2	0.349808	5.05841	4.96974	
	3	0.0696602	2.46945	2.0733	
	4	0.159355	4.30356	3.89713	
4	1	1.48134	6.29862	6.22215	
	2	1.45387	7.98695	9.16905	0.280826
	3	1.4586	8.32985	7.12115	
	4	1.51232	4.51151	7.20504	0.260738
5	1	0.920654	5.6189	32.7935	0.286951
	2	1.08154	11.3604	22.2376	
	3	0.927155	10.9472	26.9463	
	4	0.934761	4.04755	35.9284	0.279433
6	1	5.63073	11.1478	34.1265	
	2	6.13603	20.0828	36.6363	
	3	6.57468	19.4479	35.5359	
	4	6.46806	10.2154	30.0633	
7	1	2.44676	6.78825	18.6499	
	2	2.52626	5.60084	18.7377	
	3	2.72251	4.07405	8.38101	
	4	2.8521	3.37506	10.352	0.263554
8	1	3.17241	7.96257	18.3239	23.5597

	2	2.90862	4.74479	11.4953	
	3	2.51472	8.07545	18.7715	140.098
	4	2.26567	4.65729	18.0156	
9	1	16.2596	3.60208	7.10332	100.356
	2	16.236	3.44971	7.11524	101.123
	3	16.1594	3.85441	6.70022	91.273
	4	16.2138	6.83863	8.93904	93.4374
10	1	4.77894	12.1846	17.5642	
	2	5.40763	4.75166	11.9847	19.4826
	3	5.39865	11.3998	14.1067	
	4	4.72441	11.591	14.9423	
11	1	4.45587	27.2074	25.395	
	2	5.0254	16.8457	0.0629039	
	3	6.13222	11.1292	24.1406	93.6286
	4	6.48207	8.98105	37.2316	
12	1	8.17758	7.86563	34.9437	
	2	5.78729	2.38179	4.53761	
	3	5.75668	11.5882	41.9786	
	4	5.37379	3.82274	3.01276	
13	1	5.77439	9.25852	25.7422	
	2	4.11621	18.1938	6.17775	
	3	4.50904	5.14414	8.603989	
	4	4.67577	11.9699	38.1385	
14	1	4.94564	3.20183	13.5629	160.697
	2	5.02385	5.32415	16.7389	
	3	5.09531	5.74721	19.8519	328.883
	4	5.16934	5.337	17.9985	160.359

Table 5: Raw Data Set from Preliminary Testing (Participants without Scoliosis)

PARTICIPANT	TEST	SHOULDER ANGLE DIFFERENCE	BODY ALIGNMENT	POTSI	DAPI
1	1	1.08343	6.2428	32.1918	
	2	1.2004	7.589	13.719	
	3	0.579292	10.47	9.24927	
	4	0.674271	10.0902	15.2057	
2	1	11.9696	6.95333	10.672	
	2	10.7459	1.85758	5.05433	
	3	10.7697	3.99826	13.3538	
	4	9.26821	0.881694	3.06583	
3	1	3.51031	4.42269	15.1929	
	2	0.685562	4.63418	18.6452	
	3	1.02045	4.52787	16.6398	
	4	4.45857	4.45857	17.9765	
4	1	1.38507	7.77513	17.934	
	2	1.56686	12.7252	30.4785	
	3	0.0155869	11.0064	28.7728	
	4	0.0407906	7.37197	12.208	
5	1	9.52282	15.4361	19.5332	
	2	9.0106	12.6574	22.9869	
	3	9.16245	10.9417	10.9417	
	4	9.20083	12.5209	12.5209	
6	1	6.76895	6.81006	8.93757	
	2	6.75483	3.01048	10.8724	
	3	6.82386	3.88183	7.87819	
	4	6.84475	4.01128	10.3818	
7	1	2.85982	10.9487	1.94804	
	2	2.68979	12.3189	7.21679	
	3	2.55334	6.42272	2.6566	
	4	2.39647	8.73254	5.2459	
8	1	8.97723	3.86863	15.4218	
	2	8.92971	6.1711	11.5671	
	3	8.79995	4.4706	19.7185	

	4	8.72871	4.69935	23.1435	
9	1	1.54156	9.67941	5.04949	
	2	1.67556	11.182	8.44103	
	3	1.76738	7.96535	8.85205	
	4	1.85309	4.60673	6.38753	
10	1	4.6682	4.27094	6.48714	
	2	5.48141	4.08457	7.23005	
	3	6.0616	2.3531	17.243	
	4				
11	1	7.91171	2.95117	14.7506	0.376458
	2	8.69953	2.33196	16.7429	0.368824
	3	7.8721	2.67478	14.3544	0.368536
	4	8.01245	2.29211	20.4206	infinite
12	1	5.80748	6.13577	24.3218	
	2	6.1184	5.42641	20.0787	
	3	5.26755	6.12494	16.6977	
	4	4.1691	7.06647	5.54139	

APPENDIX B

Informed Consent Form

Title of the Research: Using Kinect to Detect Scoliosis with Machine Learning

Principal Investigators: Jose Ignacio Locsin

Christine Okubo

Romeo Quisto

Name of Organization: Philippine Science High School – Main Campus

PART I. INFORMATION SHEET

PURPOSE

Scoliosis is a physical deformity characterized by the rotation of the spine. It can appear as early as in childhood and worsens with time if left untreated, making early detection vital. Standard diagnosis methods are often costly and make use of expensive equipment and X-ray imaging techniques, which expose the patient to radiation. Additionally, diagnosis should be conducted by experts, this study “Using Kinect™ to Detect Scoliosis with Machine Learning” aims to create an alternative scoliosis-detection method using the Kinect™. It is an advanced game sensor which incorporates three types of cameras: color, depth and infrared. The Kinect™ sensor has many applications outside the gaming industry due to its capabilities which includes body tracking and 3D mapping. This alternative method is non-invasive and eliminates the need for X-ray imaging and enables detection even in the absence of physicians. In addition, it uses the Kinect™ sensor, which is relatively affordable and therefore easily accessible. As a result, the developed method is cheaper, safer, and more accessible, as well as faster. This facilitates the early detection and treatment of scoliosis.

PROCEDURE

The completion of the study requires that we subject our program to two testing stages: the initial testing, from which the training and calibration data will be taken from, and the final testing, which will determine the accuracy of our program. We need forty (40) students for the initial testing and sixty (60) students for the final testing. The forty (40) students will be equally divided into males and females in which there will be ten (10) with scoliosis and ten (10) without scoliosis for both genders. The sixty (60) students will also be equally divided into males and females with fifteen (15) scoliotic and fifteen (15) non-scoliotic for both genders. We would also need access to medical records related to scoliosis, if available, to reassure that we would be able to collect verifiable results.

Your child will be asked to participate in only one procedure and you may accompany him/her if

you choose to do so.

The procedure is as follows:

- The testing will be conducted in a private room.
- Your child will be asked to position himself/herself facing the wall with his/her back facing the entrance, and to take off ALL his/her upper garments. Girls may choose to wear an adhesive bra provided by the group, or they may decide to provide their own. During this time, the researcher will remain outside the room to allow your child to position himself/herself comfortably.
- Testing will be done by a researcher of the same gender as your child. The procedure for female participants will be handled by Christine Okubo. Jay-ai Locsin will be handling the procedure for male participants.
- A bell will be provided. Once your child is ready, he/she may ring the bell to signal that the researcher may enter. The Kinect™ sensor will be placed 1.5-2 meters from his/her back. The depth camera of a Kinect™ sensor will be used to scan his/her back area.
- After the back scan, the researcher will leave the room to give your child time to get dressed.

If you're uncomfortable with this for any reason, please inform us, as we would be willing to make the needed adjustments.

This will be the only direct involvement of your child in the study. However, it is possible that we try to contact you again in the future to ask for permission regarding the use of the gathered data.

POTENTIAL HEALTH/ DIRECT BENEFITS

Should you choose to participate, there will be no direct benefit to your child. The testing is not therapeutic and is solely for scoliosis detection. Any benefits resulting from this study will be for the community as a whole in the creation of a scoliosis detection method that will promote the easy and early detection of scoliosis.

POTENTIAL HEALTH RISKS

There are no potential health risks. The only equipment involved are the Kinect™ sensor and a posture guide. Your child will not be exposed to radiation or any potentially harmful substances during the procedure and will not be asked to exert any strenuous effort. The potential health risks will be equivalent to the day-to-day potential risks a person experiences.

FINANCIAL ELEMENTS

Your child will not incur any costs through his/her participation in the study.

ALTERNATIVES TO PARTICIPATING/ RIGHT TO REFUSE/WITHDRAW

Participation in this study is voluntary and includes the right to decide to withdraw anytime. We will gladly answer any questions you may have. If there is anything you wish to clarify, please don't hesitate to ask. If any part of the study is left unclear to you, you will not be held to your consent.

WITHDRAWAL FROM THE RESEARCH

Your child may decide to terminate his/her participation in the study at any point prior to its publication. Termination of his participation would mean that he/she would no longer need to undergo the testing procedure. Should you have already gone through the testing, the data gathered will not be used in our study. However, once our study is published, we will not be able to remove any data included. As such, we require that we be informed of requests to terminate participation by April 14, 2018.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The data gathered from testing will be a depth image of your back, and any quantitative (i.e. numerical) information that may be obtained from it. It will be used only as part of our results and discussion, without any personal value attached.

Moreover, the data will be kept strictly confidential and will only be made accessible to the researchers who handled the procedure. We will ask for your consent before using any of the data gathered for any purposes that would require it to be made public. Rest assured, all data gathered from this procedure shall be used ONLY for the study it is currently part of.

As our standard protocol, we will share the information only with the participant and his or her parents/guardian/whoever assists him/her in his/her participation. Should the participant have made the decision alone, the researchers will share the information with him/her only. Under any circumstances, the choice to share your own/your child's data will be subject to your discretion. If you do so, the group shall not take responsibility for any leakage or misuse of said data.

ASKING QUESTIONS ON THE RESEARCH: WHO TO CONTACT

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CONSENT FORM

The proposal for this study, which covers the objectives, significance, and methodology, has been approved by our research adviser, Mr. Jason Alcaez and our research teacher, Mr. McJervis Villaruel. The ethical aspect was reviewed by Mr. Chuckie Fer Calsado, Chair of Ethics Committee at PSHS.

Your child will only be participating in the initial testing.

____ I have fully read and understood the contents of this study.

____ I hereby agree to participate in this study.

____ I do not wish to participate in this study.

Name and Signature of Student

Name & Signature of Parent/Guardian

Contact Details

Date

APPENDIX C

Letter to Doctor

DR. JOSE BRITANICO PUJALTE JR.

Director of Philippine Orthopedic Center

Dear Dr. Pujalte,

Greetings!

We are conducting a study entitled **“Using Kinect to Detect Scoliosis with Applied Machine Learning”**. Our research group consists of Jay-ai Locsin, Christine Okubo, and Romeo Quisto of Philippine Science High School - Main Campus (PSHS-MC). This letter serves as a request for you to be our reference person regarding scoliosis in the Philippines.

The objective of our research is to be able to create an alternative method of detecting scoliosis that will be fast, cheap and free of radiation exposure. We will be using the Xbox Kinect V2 for its depth sensing and body tracking capabilities. Three of the more popular optical methods for assessing scoliosis: shoulder asymmetry, the Posterior Trunk Symmetry Index (POTSI) and the Deformity in the Axial Plane Index (DAPI) will be used and put into code for automation. Attached herewith is a summary of our research project.

We would like to know your insights regarding scoliosis mainly about the process of diagnosis in the Philippines. Furthermore, questions regarding treatment, its difference from other spinal curvature issues and social impacts will be asked. We believe that your expertise will help us in achieving the objectives of our project.

Thank you very much.

Respectfully yours,

Jay-ai Locsin
Grade 11 Student
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APPENDIX D

Sample Code

//Shoulder Angle code snippet

```
inline float Kinect::findAngle(Joint start, Joint center, Joint end) {
    float a = sqrt(pow(start.Position.X - center.Position.X, 2) + pow(start.Position.Y -
center.Position.Y, 2));
    float b = sqrt(pow(end.Position.X - center.Position.X, 2) + pow(end.Position.Y -
center.Position.Y, 2));
    float c = sqrt(pow(start.Position.X - end.Position.X, 2) + pow(start.Position.Y -
end.Position.Y, 2));
    return acos((a*a + b*b - c*c) / (2 * a*b))*180/PI;
}
```

//Body Alignment code snippet

```
for (int y = (int)floor(start.Y); y < (int)floor(end.Y); ++y)
{
    float x1 = 0, x2 = 0;

    for (int x = start.X; x > 1; x--)
    {
        if ((clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[0] != 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[1]
!= 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[2] != 0))
        {
            x1 = x;
            break;
        }
    }
    for (int x = start.X; x < depthWidth-1; x++)
    {
        if ((clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[0] != 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[1]
!= 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[2] != 0))
        {
            x2 = x;
            break;
        }
    }
    spine.insert(i, (x1 + x2) / 2);
}
```

DAPI code snippets

```
float d1=1, d2=1;
```

```
float sslope = (LSD.Y - RSD.Y) / (LSD.X - RSD.X);  
int smidy = (int)round(sslope * (mid.X - LSD.X) + LSD.Y);  
int smidx = (int)mid.X;
```

```
float wslope = (LWD.Y - RWD.Y) / (LWD.X - RWD.X);  
int wmidy = (int)round(wslope * (mid.X - LWD.X) + LWD.Y);  
int wmidx = (int)mid.X;
```

```
char blah[64];
```

```
try {  
    if (LeftScapulaPoint->Z <= RightScapulaPoint->Z)  
    {  
        int primeX = (int)(smidx + 2*(LSD.X - smidx));  
        int primeY = (int)(smidy + 2*(LSD.Y - smidy));  
        if ((primeX < 0) || (primeY < 0))  
        {  
            OutputDebugString("LSabort");  
            return 1;  
        }  
        LeftScapulaPrime = pic[(primeY * depthWidth) + primeX];  
        d1 = abs(LeftScapulaPoint->Z - LeftScapulaPrime.Z);  
    }  
    else  
    {  
        int primeX = (int)(smidx + 2 * (RSD.X - smidx));  
        int primeY = (int)(smidy + 2 * (RSD.Y - smidy));  
        if ((primeX < 0) || (primeY < 0))  
        {  
            OutputDebugString("RSabort");  
            return 1;  
        }  
        RightScapulaPrime = pic[(primeY * depthWidth) + primeX];  
        d1 = abs(RightScapulaPoint->Z - RightScapulaPrime.Z);  
    }  
  
    if (LeftTrunkPoint->Z < RightTrunkPoint->Z)  
    {  
        int primeX = (int)(wmidx + 2*(LWD.X - wmidx));  
        int primeY = (int)(wmidy + 2*(LWD.Y - wmidy));  
        if ((primeX < 0) || (primeY < 0))
```

```

    {
        OutputDebugString("Labort");
        return 1;
    }
    sprintf(blah, "L %p\n", LeftWaistPrime);
    OutputDebugString(blah);

    sprintf(blah, "L %d %d %d", primeY, depthWidth, primeX);
    OutputDebugString(blah);

    LeftWaistPrime = pic[(primeY * depthWidth) + primeX];

    //sprintf(blah, "L %p\n", LeftWaistPrime);
    //OutputDebugString(blah);

    d2 = abs(LeftTrunkPoint->Z - LeftWaistPrime.Z);
}
else
{
    int primeX = (int)(wmidx + 2 * (RWD.X - wmidx));
    int primeY = (int)(wmidy + 2 * (RWD.Y - wmidy));
    if ((primeX < 0) || (primeY < 0))
    {
        return 1;
    }
    d2 = abs(RightTrunkPoint->Z - RightWaistPrime.Z);
}

```

POTSI code snippets

```

float LeftAxillaDistance = 10000;
int LeftAxillaX = 1;
int LeftAxillaY = 1;
for (int y = (int)floor(Ls.Y); y < (int)floor(mid.Y); ++y)
{
    for (int x = 1; x < mid.X ; x++)
    {
        if ((clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[0] != 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[1]
!= 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(x, y))[2] != 0))
        {
            float distance = pow(Ls.X - x, 2) + pow(Ls.Y - y, 2);
            if (distance <= LeftAxillaDistance)
            {
                LeftAxillaDistance = distance;
                LeftAxillaX = x;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        LeftAxillaY = y;
    }
}
}

float RightAcromionSlope = (Rs.Y - RightAxillaY) / (Rs.X - RightAxillaX);
int RightAcromionX = 1;
int RightAcromionY = 1;

for (int abscissa = Rs.X; abscissa < depthWidth; abscissa++) {
    int ordinate1 = ceil(RightAcromionSlope*(abscissa - Rs.X) + Rs.Y);
    int ordinate2 = floor(RightAcromionSlope*(abscissa - Rs.X) + Rs.Y);

    if ((clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(abscissa, ordinate1))[0] != 0) &&
        (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(abscissa, ordinate1))[1] != 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(abscissa,
        ordinate1))[2] != 0))
    {
        RightAcromionX = abscissa;
        RightAcromionY = ordinate1;
        break;
    }

    else if ((clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(abscissa, ordinate2))[0] != 0) &&
        (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(abscissa, ordinate2))[1] != 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(abscissa,
        ordinate2))[2] != 0))
    {
        RightAcromionX = abscissa;
        RightAcromionY = ordinate2;
        break;
    }
}

//Trunk Points
int LTX = 1;
int RTX = 1;
int LeftTrunkX = 1;
int LeftTrunkY = 1;
int RightTrunkX = 1;
int RightTrunkY = 1;
int minLeft = depthWidth;
int minRight = depthWidth;

for (int n = mid.Y; n < end.Y; n++)
{

```

```

    for (int i = NatalCLeftX; i > 0; i--)
    {
        if ((clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(i, n))[0] != 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(i, n))[1]
!= 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(i, n))[2] != 0))
        {
            LTX = i;
            break;
        }
    }
    for (int i = NatalCLeftX; i < depthWidth; i++)
    {
        if ((clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(i, n))[0] != 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(i, n))[1]
!= 0) && (clr.at<Vec3b>(Point(i, n))[2] != 0))
        {
            RTX = i;
            break;
        }
    }

    if (minLeft > abs(LTX - NatalCLeftX))
    {
        minLeft = abs(LTX - NatalCLeftX);
        LeftTrunkX = LTX;
        LeftTrunkY = n;
    }
    if (minRight > abs(RTX - NatalCLeftX))
    {
        minRight = abs(RTX - NatalCLeftX);
        RightTrunkX = RTX;
        RightTrunkY = n;
    }

}

```